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ROAD TO SPARKLING HAIR WITH NO SHAMPOO**Uzbekistan State World Languages University,****Ozodakhon Izzatillaeva**

Annotation: In this article, I will share my research on effects of shampoo on hair health and look into scientifically-proven and practiced benefits of not using it. I will also be discussing how it is possible to adopt no shampoo approach effectively.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada men shampunning soch sog'lig'iga ta'siri bo'yicha tadqiqotlarim bilan o'rtoqlashaman va uni ishlatmaslikning ilmiy jihatdan tasdiqlangan va amaliy foydalarini ko'rib chiqaman. Bundan tashqari, qanday qilib shampunsiz yondashuvni samarali yo'lga qo'yish mumkinligini muhokama qilaman.

Аннотация: В этой статье я поделюсь своим исследованием влияния шампуня на здоровье волос и рассмотрю научно доказанные и практические преимущества отказа от его использования. Я также буду обсуждать, как можно эффективно применять подход без шампуня.

Key words: natural extracts, cosmetics market, no poo approach, conditioners, hair health, anti-shampoo.

Ключевые слова: натуральные экстракты, рынок косметики, подход без шампуня, кондиционеры, здоровье волос, антишампунь.

Kalit so'zlar: tabiiy ekstraktlar, kosmetika bozori, shampunsiz yondashuv, konditsionerlar, soch salomatligi, anti-shampun.

Over the last couple of decades, shampoos and conditioners have become an irreplaceable part of our showers. Unsurprisingly, before even a century ago, apart from the upper class of society, common people didn't know what shampoo was, let alone use one. Majority of them would use plain water to wash their hair, along with some natural oils or extracts if they come from a more prominent background. Now back to 2023, male or female, it's hard to imagine going without shampoo for weeks, let alone months. Mere idea of smelly, greasy and unkempt hair is unpleasant. Despite that, there have been campaigns under the banner of "no poo" - no shampoo, in recent years, because as the hair cosmetics market bloomed year by year and different variations of hair products have been produced, some people became skeptical about the actual necessity of such merchandise. The supporters of no poo claim that over advertisement of companies and bias toward using no shampoo is no more than an elaborate scheme to make people buy more. Nat Eliason, one of those supporters of anti-shampoo

movement, post on his vlog: "Quitting mostly happened on accident, but now that I've seen just how unnecessary shampoo ever was to my hair's health and appearance, I don't see myself ever going back", and he is quite adamant about it. Nat claims that quitting shampoo gives you healthier hair and easier time styling. The most attractive thing that made me interested in giving up shampoo is his comment about how hair condition reveals our health and how much of an obstruction shampoo is to that process: "Here's a big one: once you stop shampooing and conditioning your hair, it will reveal your health. If you eat poorly, undersleep, stop exercising, get stressed out, your hair will show it. It'll get darker, more oily, your scalp will get dryer, it'll get unhealthier with you." After coming across Nat's article, I decided to do a little research and in this article

I'll be listing how helpful no poo is in different terms and how to implement this practice to your life.

People who want to adopt the no poo approach don't always have the same purposes for doing so. In the article by Taylor Norris, it is said that some want to avoid overly stripping their hair of good and natural oils produced by the scalp, while others want to use fewer unnatural chemicals in their daily routines. And for some people, no poo means rejecting the commercial pressure to spend more money on hygiene than may actually be unnecessary. According to that, I concluded that apart from the biggest reason people want to quit shampoo - to make their hair more healthy and strong, anti-shampoo movement could help the pockets of millions who spend considerable finances on hair products.

When it comes to hair health, Chambers-Harris claims that over-washing hair with shampoos can not only strip the hair of its natural oils, but can also cause product build-up and toxins to enter the bloodstream, leading to myriad health issues. Mamelak also notes that water-only washing eliminates the use of sulfates, a common additive in shampoos. "Sulfates are extremely effective in removing dirt and cleaning the hair and scalp, however, many claim that they leave the hair feeling dry and brittle," he says. Products of nature like coconut milk, egg white, sour cream and others have vital elements in them that help with removing dirt, moisturizing the skin and getting rid of bacterias without harming the natural oils produced by the scalp as I have experimented. They are much more risk-free compared to over-the-counter products in terms of hair health.

Speaking of the negative impact shampoo and conditioner can have on our hair, Nicholas Garcia counts 5 huge disadvantages in her article. Namely, reducing hair longevity, causing the hair to go frizz, locking you into catch 22 situation (situation in which you can't part with shampoo because it has already broken your cycle and you're overly dependant on it), wastefulness and its incapability to be washed out since our scalp absorbs whatever is in the poured onto it with water. What intrigued me was that fifth point. Nicholas explains about that point, saying "This is just a bit ironic. Shampoo washes out just about everything from your hair except for itself. Your hair is porous, and so over time it absorbs whatever is in your shampoo like a sponge. If you're using a cheap shampoo, or one with chemicals that doesn't mix well with your scalp, you'll run into problems. The only way to really get the shampoo gunk off your head is to either use a super strong shampoo made specifically for that, or just wait it out and let your scalp dispose of it naturally."

At the end of the day, the choice to either use a shampoo or not to use it is purely yours. However, if you're willing to persevere with oily and seemingly dirty hair for a couple of weeks, you'll be able to see visible results that surprise you. After you've given up shampoo and conditioners, with the help of natural fragrance oils your hair will start to look stunning and gorgeous as it ever had, since without the obstruction of chemicals it'll have better absorption and healing rate. Of course, this is my personal hypothesis derived from a number of scientific articles on the subject. If you have the desire to make an effort for healthy and strong hair, adopt the no poo approach from today on.

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